

Pacemaker and Geriatric Anaesthesia: A special report

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ABSTRACT

Geriatrics or geriatric medicine is a speciality in the medical field that focuses on health care of older adults. Anaesthesia for geriatric patients is quite challenging. Understanding anaesthetic care for older patients can be related to the description of fundamental alterations in physiology and changes in the pharmacokinetics and pharmacodynamics of anaesthetic medications. Cardiac pacemakers are generally required in patients with symptomatic bradycardia or severe conduction block. We present the anesthetic management of a case of an elderly male patient, posted for bilateral inguinal hernioplasty having a permanent pacemaker in situ in DDDR (dual-chamber rate-modulated) mode. The pacemaker was changed inserted previously for complete atrioventricular (AV) block on electrocardiogram (ECG) and degenerative AV conduction disease with complete symptomatic AV (atrioventricular) block, on electrophysiology study. The pacemaker mode changed to VOO (asynchronous ventricular pacing) mode preoperatively. Central neuraxial blockade was given. Beat-to-beat haemodynamic monitoring was instituted with the invasive arterial catheter-transducer system. The patient tolerated the surgical procedure well, and vital parameters were maintained throughout the operation. Phenylephrine infusion was given briefly to maintain the blood pressure (Mean Arterial Pressure (MAP) > 65mmHg). After the operation, the patient was shifted to the intensive care unit (ICU), the pacemaker was reprogrammed to DDDR mode, and vigilant monitoring was done. The patient was then transferred to the ward on the 2nd postoperative day in a stable condition. This case highlights that low-dose spinal anaesthesia along with vigilant monitoring is a reasonable choice for elderly patients with permanent pacemakers coming for elective surgeries.

KEYWORDS Geriatric anaesthesia, Pacemaker mode, Central neuraxial block, Phenylephrine, Complete AV block, Central neuraxial block

Introduction

Artificial (permanent) pacemaker patients scheduled for non-cardiac surgery require special considerations for preoperative evaluation and subsequent management of anaesthesia. Pre-

anaesthetic assessment includes evaluation and optimisation of coexisting diseases. In our case, after taking cardiology opinion, pacemaker mode was changed to ventricular paced- none sensed - no response mode. ECG monitoring must include the ability to detect pacing discharges; patient monitoring must include the ability to ensure that paced electrical activity is converted to mechanical systole which is best evaluated by pulse oximetry, plethysmography or arterial pressure waveform display. Some patients may require increased pacing rate intra-operatively to meet an increased oxygen demand scenario, and appropriate equipment must be ready to provide backup pacing or defibrillation.

DDDR (dual-chamber rate-modulated) mode [1] is a relatively recent addition in pacemaker electrophysiology, wherein it tracks the patient's intrinsic P wave as well as the AV sequential sensor-indicated rate response. We at this moment present the anaesthetic management and peri-operative considerations

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in geriatric patients on pacemaker during regional anaesthesia.

Case Report

An elderly male patient aged 75 years with a permanent cardiac pacemaker for five years was posted for open bilateral inguinal hernioplasty. The patient underwent all routine investigations required for the proposed surgery which was within normal limits. The patient presented with a history of syncopal attacks five years back, for which he was admitted and evaluated in a hospital and found to have third-degree atrioventricular (AV) block on electrocardiogram (ECG). In electrophysiology study, he was diagnosed to have degenerative AV conduction disease and symptomatic complete AV block. The patient underwent permanent pacemaker implantation five years back and was in DDDR mode. The patient also had a history of high blood pressure and undergoing treatment with anti-hypertensives (Tab telmisartan 40 mg OD and tab chlorthalidone 12.5mg OD) for the last eight years. A cardiologist opinion was taken before surgery for cardiac risk stratification. Cardiac monitoring during surgery was advocated, and the pacemaker mode was changed to Ventricle paced, none-sensed, no response (VOO mode). On examination, the patient was around 60 kg with 165 cm height. He had no symptoms or signs of cardio-respiratory failure. Airway and spine examination were within normal limits. All blood investigations were within normal limits, including serum electrolytes.

Special attention was given to cautery, where only bipolar cautery was permitted in short bursts, with the cautery pads placed away from the pacemaker device. Pacemaker reprogramming was planned to be done after surgery. On the day of surgery, the patient was shifted to operation theatre, all (standard ASA) monitors attached, and baseline parameters were recorded. A 16G intravenous (IV) cannula was secured in the right dorsum of the hand. The pacemaker was programmed to (VOO) mode on the day of surgery and heart was paced at 90 beats per min. Pre-induction left radial artery cannulation was done using Seldinger technique and connected to transducer system for invasive beat-to-beat arterial pressure monitoring. The central neuraxial block was given under all aseptic precautions using 25 G spinal needle with 2ml of 0.5% heavy Bupivacaine (12.5mg) and 25 mcg Fentanyl Citrate (opioid) in subarachnoid space, at L3-L4 inter-space. Block level to T10 was achieved. The patient underwent open bilateral hernioplasty with the use of bipolar cautery with low current. Vitals were maintained within 20% of baseline with intravenous phenylephrine (200µg/hour) infusion, which was started after spinal anaesthesia to prevent and treat hypotension, along with intravenous fluids. The heart was paced at 90 per min by the pacemaker. In the post-operative period, the patient was shifted to the ICU for vigilant monitoring. Post-op investigations were within normal limits. The pacemaker was reprogrammed to DDDR mode. The patient was observed in the ICU for 24-hours, and later shifted to the ward in a stable condition, and was advised regular follow-up with the cardiology team.

Discussion

The permanent cardiac pacing was initially designed for the management of Stokes-Adams (syncopal) attacks in patients with complete heart block. Currently, the most common indication for it is sinus node dysfunction. Cardiac pacing is the only long-term the treatment for symptomatic bradycardia, regardless of the cause. Technical advances in cardiac pacing have included

the creation of dual-chamber devices, rate response algorithms, and implantable cardioverter/defibrillators. An artificial cardiac pacemaker system consists of a device that generates electrical impulses (pulse generator) and sensing and pacing electrodes and is powered by a lithium iodide battery. Electrical impulses originating in the pulse generator are transmitted through the specialised leads to excite endocardial cells and produce a propagating wave of depolarisation in the myocardium.

The presence of an artificial cardiac pacemaker in a patient scheduled for surgery unrelated to the device introduces special considerations for preoperative evaluation and subsequent management of anaesthesia. Preoperative evaluation of the patient includes determining the reason for device placement and assessment of its current function. Most of these patients belong to the elderly age group, necessitating the anesthesiologist to follow principles of geriatric anaesthesia [2]. In a patient with a cardiac pacemaker, preoperative evaluation and peri-operative planning should be coordinated with a cardiologist and the pacemaker representative for that specific device. A preoperative history of vertigo, pre-syncope or syncope in a patient with a pacemaker could reflect pacemaker dysfunction. Vigilant monitoring of ECG, pulse oximetry and arterial blood pressure should be done. The NASPE/BPEG (North-American Society of Pacing and Electrophysiology/British Pacing and Electrophysiology Group) nomenclature [3] is used to describe the various (A, atrial; V, ventricular; D, dual chamber) characteristics of cardiac pacemakers. The first letter denotes the cardiac chamber(s) being paced, the second letter denotes the cardiac chamber(s) that detects (senses) electrical signals (A, atrial; V, ventricular; D, dual chamber), the third letter indicates the response to sensed signals (I, inhibition; T, triggering; D, dual: inhibition and triggering), the fourth position of the code serves to describe the presence or absence of rate modulation (R) and the fifth letter of the code denotes the chamber(s) in which multisite pacing is delivered. The most common pacing modes are AAI, VVI and DDD. Improved shielding of cardiac pacemakers has reduced the problems associated with electromagnetic interference (EMI) from electrocautery. A pacemaker can sense the electrical artefact produced by electrocautery as either interference or an intrinsic R wave. If the pacemaker senses interference and is not certain whether an R wave is being produced, the unit will go into asynchronous (fixed rate) mode to guarantee delivery of a paced beat.

Alternately, the electrical artefact from electrocautery could be sensed as an R wave resulting in inhibition of the pulse generator. The grounding electrode for electrocautery should be as far as possible from the pulse generator to minimise detection of the cautery current by the pulse generator. It is also useful to keep the electrocautery current as low as possible and to apply electrocautery in short bursts, especially if the current is being applied near the pulse generator. While using electrocautery, precaution for minimal EMI [4] (electromagnetic interference) should be taken (bipolar cautery or harmonic is to be used preferentially). The magnet should not be placed over pacemaker in the OT in the presence of electrocautery. Rate responsive pacemakers should have their rate-responsive mode disabled before surgery. Provision of temporary pacing should be available in the OT to deal with the emergency situation of pacemaker malfunction. Pacemaker should be rechecked for proper functioning and battery after the procedure.

Phenylephrine Hydrochloride [5] is a direct α_1 -adrenergic receptor agonist (α_1 specific), increasing the systemic vascular

resistance (SVR) and arterial blood pressure. Literature reports that in preload-dependent patients, due to relative hypovolemia induced by central neuraxial and general anaesthesia, in leg-down position, phenylephrine may increase cardiac preload by centralisation of blood volume, in addition to its effects on increasing the afterload. The ultimate goal of hemodynamic monitoring is to ensure adequate tissue perfusion and oxygenation, which is possible only by maintaining perfusion pressures and stable mean arterial pressures. Phenylephrine infusion can be given prophylactically to prevent anaesthesia-induced hypotension, as it does not cause reflex tachycardia or hypertension. Excess of intravenous fluids to counter hypotension is deleterious in elderly with cardiac problems. Hence, phenylephrine infusion was used in our case to avoid hypotension following spinal anaesthesia.

Conclusion

Anesthetic management of patients with cardiac pacemakers posted for non-cardiac procedures requires thorough understanding about the indication of pacemaker insertion, various modes of pacing, and programming of the pacemaker. A cardiologist should also be consulted for device evaluation regarding its proper function and life of the batteries. Anaesthetic management should be planned preoperatively according to patient's medical status. In addition to standard monitors, invasive arterial pressure monitoring may be required. Regional anaesthesia with vigilant monitoring can be a good choice for the elderly patient with a permanent cardiac pacemaker coming for elective non-cardiac surgery.

Competing Interests

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

1. Hayes DL, Higano ST, Eisinger G. Electrocardiographic manifestations of a dual-chamber, rate-modulated [DDDR] pacemaker. *Pacing Clin Electrophysiol.*1989;12(4 Pt 1):555-62.
2. Govindaswamy S, Geetha S. Anaesthesia management of an elderly patient having permanent pacemaker for total hip replacement. *Karnataka Anaesth J* 2015;1:194-5.
3. Bernstein AD, Daubert JC, Fletcher RD, Sutton R. The revised NASPE/BPEG generic code for anti-bradycardia, adaptive-rate, and multisite pacing. North American Society of Pacing and Electrophysiology/British Pacing and Electrophysiology Group. *Pacing and Clinical Electrophysiology* 2002;25(2):260-4.
4. Stone ME, Salter B, Fischer A. Perioperative management of patients with cardiac implantable electronic devices. *Br J Anaesth* 2011;107(1):i16 – i26.
5. Ertmer C, Morelli A, Westphal M. (2009) The Role of Phenylephrine in Perioperative Medicine. In: Vincent JL. (eds) *Yearbook of Intensive Care and Emergency Medicine*. Yearbook of Intensive Care and Emergency Medicine, vol 2009. Springer, Berlin, Heidelberg.